
**BRIDGING THEORY AND PRACTICE IN SUSTAINABLE
DEVELOPMENT FOR POST-CONFLICT SOCIETIES: NORTH-EAST
NIGERIA CASE**

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ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
<p>One of the most cherished aspirations of every society emerging from conflict is its ability to transform, bounce back and attain sustainable development in the post-conflict period. No society indicate or abhors lack of willingness to achieve such a noble dream. In Nigeria, the crises of Boko Haram led to the destruction of properties and communities, death of persons, and displacement of millions of individuals. The violent conflict has destroyed several livelihood sources and made many rich individuals poor and destitute and as well sent many young people, women and children into their untimely graves. This paper examines the attainment of sustainable development in post-conflict societies with focus on North-East Nigeria. The paper is hinged on conceptual and theoretical approach to examining the postconflict state of attaining sustainable development using secondary data derived from published and unpublished sources with analysis based of thematic approach using document analysis. The focus of the paper is on the ravaging violent conflict by the Boko Haram insurgents in the by addressing the key fundamental issues including the phases of conflicts management and recovery, the strategies for the attainment of sustainable development and economic prosperity in the post conflict society, the key actors and strategic stakeholders in the post conflict recovery and reconstructions, and the challenges confronting sustainable development in the post-conflict society.</p>	<p>development, sustainable development, conflict, post-conflict societies,</p>

INTRODUCTION

Attaining sustainable development in post conflict society is one of the most cherished aspiration of every society emerging from conflict situation. This is so because there is no record of single society or group that abhors or demonstrate lack of willingness to achieve such noble dreams throughout human historical evolution. Within the context of Nigeria in general and North-East region in particular, sustainable development agenda in a post conflict society is not only relevant and timely but also reflect our contemporary reality. This is because the polity

and indeed some countries in Africa are engulfed in serious conflict dynamics albeit of different dimension and intensity.

In Nigeria, for instance, there is none out of the six geo-political zones that does not have its peculiar form of violent conflict or a combination of two or more. Of particular interests are the Boko Haram insurgency and farmer – herder conflict in North-East Nigeria; the armed banditry and menace of kidnaping for ransom in North-West Nigeria; ethno- religious violence and farmer – herder conflict and banditry in North-Central Nigeria; the Namdi Kanu led separatist agitation by the Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB) in the South-East Nigeria; the Niger-Delta agitation for resource control in the South-South region; and of recent, the Sunday Igboho led agitation for sovereign state of Odudua and many other ethno-religious conflicts in the South-West of Nigeria. The first quarter of the 21st century has witnessed gradual but steadily increase in global turmoil and instability most especially the ever growing tide of violent conflicts. Although conflict has for ages became part and parcel of human evolutionary history spanning different phases of human civilization and geo-entity, such conflicts varies in nature, triggers, dynamics, dimension and intensity from one society and generation to another. This means that each society and generation experience different types of conflicts depending on their individual local peculiarities. There is common ground among scholars and conflict experts alike that although triggers and intensity of conflicts varies across civilization time and space but that conflicts arise out of incompatibility of interest which could be in the area of politics and power, economic resources as well as clashes over dominance of vital societal norms and value.

Although conflict especially violent conflict has destroyed several civilizations, made many rich individuals poor and destitute and as well sent many young people, women and children into their untimely graves. Yet, many conflict scholars especially those influenced by the radical Marxian strand believes that conflict is the hallmark of every civilization if any meaningful change and development could take place. The dominant view of this group of scholars is that conflict is an indispensable part of human existence even though their analysis is hinged on the paradigm of class antagonism framework. Thus irrespective of framework of analysis one glaring area of congruence among conflict scholars and theorists is that conflict though undesirable is a permanent scar with which every group of individuals and communities must learn how to live. If that is so Nigeria as a sovereign state that is made up plural complex ethno-religious and cultural heterogeneity cannot by any standard be an exceptions. This in part explain why Nigeria throughout its tortuous process of struggle to nationhood and nation building is embedded in series and plethora of violent conflicts ranging from the needless and avoidable 30 months bloody civil war between 1967 to 1970, the seven days irredentism of Adaka Boro in the Niger delta, several sectarian crises including the Zangon Kataf crises, the Kano riots, the Maitatsine crisis, the Kaduna Sharia crises, the several ethno-religious violence in Jos, the Ife Modakeke crisis, among others.

Of all these conflicts the most devastating violent conflicts Nigeria is currently witnessing is the Boko Haram insurgency which has continued to claim lives and property in the North-East region. Even though varying figures exist on the number of lives lost and properties destroyed, it is however certain that the figures run into thousands and millions, respectively. As often times, there could be under reporting and sensational reporting as well. This upsurge in violent conflict have created one of the serious humanitarian crises in the history of mankind. Such mindless and avoidable conflict has sent thousands of people into untimely graves, destruction of properties worth hundreds of millions and displacement of million people.

This insurgency has cost the people of the region their lives, initiated and sustained a steady stream of displacement and the loss of valuable properties, cultural artefacts and sites, as well as the total or in some cases

the partial destruction, disorganisation and crippling of existing cultural norms, values and beliefs systems. The three states mostly affected by the Boko haram insurgency in the North-East are Borno, Adamawa and Yobe States (BAYS). The statistical proportional distribution of displaced persons is mainly from Borno State with 62 per cent, Adamawa State 18 per cent and Yobe State with 13 per cent (IRIN, 2014). These displaced persons are either living in state-controlled camps or with host communities and relatives, in conditions far below international minimum standards. Thus the focus of this paper is on the ravaging violent conflict by the Boko Haram insurgents in the Northeast Nigeria by addressing the key fundamental issues including the phases of conflicts management and recovery, the strategies for the attainment of sustainable development and economic prosperity in the post conflict society, the key actors and strategic stakeholders in the post conflict recovery and reconstructions, and the challenges confronting sustainable development in the post conflict society.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This paper is basically theoretical and exploratory in nature. For this reason, the paper relied on library documentation analysis as the sources of data. In this respect, secondary sources including both published and unpublished materials from both open access resources and other sources were utilized. Such data were analyzed thematically using document analysis.

Development

Development as a concept no doubt is not only the most commonly used term in every day practice by all and sundry, but the most cherished state of affairs towards which individuals, communities and states strive. Although there is common consensus on the indispensability of development in human aspirations, what is not certain is the exact meaning of the subject matter. The literature on development has been entangled in a complex web of intellectual nuances and polemics. This is because the concept is explained from different dimensions and it could mean different things to different people.

Fig. 1: Conceptualization of Development

Source: Summer and Tribe (2008) cited in Joel (2016)

The first conceptualization according to the illustration above is that development is a process of structural and societal change. The key characteristics of this perspective are that it is focused on process of structural societal change. It is historical and it has a long-term outlook. This means a major societal shift in one dimension, for example from a rural or agricultural based society (sometimes called the shift from traditional to modern characteristics). This change would also have radical implications in another dimension such as societal structural changes in the perspective propositions of classes and groups within the relations of production. This means that development involves changes in socio economic structures i.e. ownership and organization of production, technology, the institutional structure and laws (Joel, 2016).

The second perspective on development views it as a short to medium term outcome of desirable targets. As its most basic level, it is simply concerned with development as occurring in terms of a set of short to medium term performance indicators i.e. goals or outcomes which can be measured and compared with targets e.g. changes in poverty or income levels. The significant feature of this conceptualization is that it is focused on the outcomes of changes so that it has a relatively short term outlook. This is however problematic to many of the academic members of the development community because it presupposes a set of goals or objectives which may not be shared by many of the people who are supposedly benefiting from development. In other words, the objectives and values expressed in the articulation of the targets of goals in this perspective hardly contain the inputs of the beneficiaries and therefore it cannot elicit the support and participation of the civil society. This perspective cannot achieve the grand vision of transformed society.

The third conceptualization of development views it as a dominant discourse of western modernity. Unlike the first two perspectives that are based on visions of change and outcome, this perspective is based on the view that development consisted of bad change and bad outcomes through the imposition of western ethnocentric notions of development upon the third world countries. This perspective emerged as a reaction to the deliberate efforts of progress made in the name of development since World War II. Thus, the modernization perspective elaborates on two main categories of societies in the world, namely the traditional and modern societies. Theorists argue that the traditional societies are entangled by norms, beliefs and values which are hindering their development process. Therefore, they must adapt the modern style of living, thus concentrate on accumulation of capital and industrialization.

In essence, this theory seeks to improve the standard of living of inferior societies, that is, improves the economic growth of supposed traditional societies to acquire basic and secondary necessities of life, by introducing modern technology and economic strategy to the third world. Modernization theorist, Rostow, also proposed swift machineries of transition for traditional societies to develop; these are preparation to take-off, take-off, and drive to maturity and the period of mass consumption. These transitional path processes put traditional societies on the development path. Again, the theory succeeds in the idea that the norms, values and beliefs of a society can affect the social change of that society. Despite the advantages attributed to the theory, it has weaknesses which must be addressed. Firstly, the theory seeks to entail only the economic and concrete industrial growth of the third world countries. The theory lacks

Amartya's view of development, which states that "development can be seen as the process of expanding the freedoms that people enjoy" (Sen,1999). To Sen, development entails freedom, liberty, and self-esteem of humanity which are neglected by the theory.

The dependency perspective on the other hand opposes the modernization theory. Its main argument is that, the persistent increment in industrialization in the developed countries rather equally subject poor countries to underdevelopment as a result of the economic surplus of the poor countries being exploited by developed countries. It was a great analysis done by Frank A. Gunder by being able to debunk the weak, non-historical and ethnocentric issues propounded by the modernization theory (Webster, 1984). Also, Gunder (as cited in Webster, 1984), succeeded in pointing out the economic inequalities among the developed and the developing countries, as well as the rampant internal inequalities in the various periphery countries and the exploitation of economic surplus developing countries during colonialism. Again, the theory posits an essence emphasis on the fact that development is not mainly based on the cultural values but rather, the economic and social structures and procedures.

Dependency theory incurs some weaknesses. Gunder failed to exhibit the specific and key dependency of the less developed countries on the metropolis, he merely stated that poor countries depend on rich countries with no specific clarification. The theory downplays internal development. It promotes the idea that indigenous industries cannot develop by its productivity which is not true. Moreover, the theory refuses to point out how the developed countries get access to the economic surplus of the third world countries.

The feminist perspective of development has its main argument being that, women have a great influence in development therefore must be empowered to partake in decision making and its implementation. This theory plays much role in the building of women capacity and capabilities as development is concerned. Also, feminists were able to bring awareness of gender inequalities among societies and engaged in massive activities to emancipate women. Feminists succeeded in propounding theories namely, Women in Development (WID) and Woman and development (WAD) to promote equity.

Despite feminists' achievement on the theory, they seemed to address the interest of females instead of addressing issues concerned with gender as a whole. This was criticized by the Gender and development theory. Also, upon all the activities and struggle to attain a high standard of living for women, there are still high inequalities among our social world unaddressed. The feminist theory failed to point out the actual actions and procedures which must be taken by the society and men to empower women in development process but just emphasized on why women must be part and neglected the "how".

To this end, Julson (2009), perceives development as a complex series of interrelated change process, abrupt and gradual, by which a population and all its component move away from pattern of life perceived in some significant ways as "less human" towards alternative patterns perceived as a "more human". Vulnerability which is a situation where a nation is exposed to forces it cannot control, is the greatest threat to development. In his view, vulnerability is enhanced by the cruel choice nations make in selecting development strategies that are devoid of morality. He regarded poverty which is an indication of vulnerability, as a kind of hell that must be avoided by nations.

Sustainable Development

The concept of sustainable development has been a subject of intellectual polemics with an increased tempo in the new millennium. Even though there are different perspectives to the concept, there is a general consensus that sustainable development involves positive changes in environmental issues, social and political developments, as well as sustaining created assets benefits. According to the International Institute for Sustainable Development (IISD) sustainable development has been defined in many ways, but the most frequently quoted definitions is from Our Common Future, also known as the Brundtland Report. It states that sustainable development is development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. It contains within it two key concepts. The concept of needs, in particular the essential needs of the world's poor, to which overriding priority should be given; and the idea of limitations imposed by the state of technology and social organization on the environment's ability to meet present and future needs.

David (1996), states that sustainable development concept consists of two major aims:

- i. The sustained economic growth that equitably meet human needs without extracting resource inputs or expelling wastes in excess of the environment's renewed capacity;
- ii. The sustained human institutions that assure both security and opportunity for social, interaction and spiritual growth life.

According to the Teachers in Development Education Annual report (2008), Sustainable development concerns a wide range of interrelated issues which may be approached through the following seven principles or

dimensions. The first concerns the interdependent nature of the word. This gives rise to the need for a participative response through the exercise of citizenship and stewardship, which is the theme of the second concept. It is in this light that

Lutzkendorf & Lorenz (2005), argued that sustainable development is ‘a journey towards a destination: ‘sustainability’ and it is a ‘triple-bottom line’ concept involving balancing economic and social development with environmental protection. It is pertinent to note that all the three dimensions of sustainable development are equal but it is the environmental dimension that is most dominant which ultimately sets the precondition for the other dimensions.

In his own postulation, Ayodele (2007), opined that sustainable development can be broadly defined as the ability of the economy to support the needs of the people of a country over a time, taking into consideration the economic, social and ecological constraints of the country. The fundamental concept is sustainable requirement, namely that the fulfilment of the needs of the present generation should not compromise the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. Thus, central to the sustainability concept is the focus on environmental phenomenon. However, there is an extension to include a consideration of social, economic, political and developmental aspects. This shows that the idea of sustainable development encompasses a deliberate process of improving human environment without impacting on the present and future generations.

Similarly, Ding (2008) argued that sustainable development is a development concerned with attitudes and judgement to help ensure long-term ecological, social, and economic growth in society. This goes to suggest that sustainability is intricately connected with the ideal of promoting a better life for everyone now and for future generations to come. In other words, sustainability may mean adapting the ways we all live and work towards meeting the needs while minimizing the impacts of consumption, providing for people of today and not endangering the generations of tomorrow.

From the above intellectual contributions, we can deduce that most literature seem to define Sustainable Development as “development that meets the needs of the present, without compromising future generations to meet their own needs. Unfortunately, Baker (2008) observed that this definition has been difficult to implement in practical terms. This limitation led Baker to formulate the definition which states that Sustainable Development is a process through which there is satisfaction of human needs while simultaneously preserving the quality of the natural environment. However, this definition does not indicate how the implementation of sustainable development can be realized. The obvious limitation about both definitions is their inability to capture the important pillars that should be emphasized if Sustainable Development is to become a relevant concept for poverty reduction. This study offers the definition that encapsulates the four indicators of Sustainable Development namely; participation, empowerment and provision of sustainable services. To this end, we can define

Sustainable Development as the kind of development that is achieved through active participation and empowerment of the individuals and their communities, which should be characterized by a strong sense of accountability and efficient utilization of resources to meet the present and future needs.

Conflict

The term conflict has been defined varyingly by social scientists and there is no dearth for definitions. Conflict appears in a social situation as any disagreement over issues of substance or emotional antagonisms that create friction between individuals or groups (Schermerhorn, 2005). The term conflict indicates a process when one party perceives that another party has negatively affected, or is about to negatively affect, something that the first party cares about (Robbins, 2006) Conflicts when kept within tolerable limits can be a source of creativity and

performance enhancement; it becomes destructive when these limits are exceeded. An optimum level of conflict needs to be maintained by an organization, i.e. there should be enough conflict to prevent stagnation, stimulate creativity, allows release of tension and initiate the seeds of change and rejuvenation, yet not so much as to be disruptive or deter coordination of activities.

Conflict may be defined as a struggle or contest between people with opposing needs, ideas, beliefs, values, or goals. Conflict on teams is inevitable; however, the results of conflict are not predetermined. Conflict might escalate and lead to non-productive results, or conflict can be beneficially resolved and lead to quality final products. Therefore, learning to manage conflict is integral to a high-performance team. Although very few people go looking for conflict, more often than not, conflict results because of miscommunication between people with regard to their needs, ideas, beliefs, goals, or values. Conflict management is the principle that all conflicts cannot necessarily be resolved, but learning how to manage conflicts can decrease the odds of non-productive escalation (Froyd, 2019). Conflict management involves acquiring skills related to conflict resolution, self-awareness about conflict modes, conflict communication skills, and establishing a structure for management of conflict in your environment.

According to Coser (1967), conflict is a struggle over values and claims to scarce status, power and resources in which the aims of the opponents are to neutralize, injure or eliminate the rivals. It is also defined from communication perspective as “an expressed struggle between at least two interdependent parties who perceive incompatible goals, scarce rewards and interference from other parties in achieving their goals (Hocker and Wilmot, 1985). In his own contribution, Abiodun (2014) views conflict as a state of discord caused by the actual or perceived opposition of needs, values and interests between formal authority and power and those individuals and groups affected. There are subtle forms of conflict involving rivalries, jealousies, personality clashes, role-definitions and struggles for power and favour. There is also conflict within individuals – between competing needs and demands – to which individuals respond in different ways.

Some scholars have contended that conflict has a divisive effect. For instance, Durkheim (cited in Osipova, 1989) considered conflict as an abnormal phenomenon. He used the term anomie or pathology to describe it. Similarly, Wilson and Kolb (1949, cited in Colser, 1964) believed that conflict has a disjunctive effect. Many other scholars have repudiated this view. Park and. Similarly, Bohannan (1967) characterizes conflict to be as basic as culture is in society, which possibly controlled and utilized profitably for better cultural development and maintenance of social order. Schellenberg (1996) states that conflict is neither bad nor good, but one of the essentials in human social life. Gluckman (1956), Gulliver (1963) and Nanda (1994) agree with the view that conflict is a part of social life and society is impossible without it. Further to this, Marxian view conflict not only as built into the social system but also as the primary stimulus for social change (Seymour-Smith, 1986).

Appelbaum, Abdallah and Shapiro (1999) further builds on this by stating that conflict is a process of social interaction. It involves a struggle over claims to resources, power and status, beliefs, preferences and desires. Abiodun (2014) linked this idea to the organization by stating that, even when conflict is a natural phenomenon in social relations, it can nevertheless be managed within companies. Additionally, Robbins (2005) has defined as —a process that begins where one party perceives that another party has negatively affected, or is about to negatively affects something that the first party cares about. This is a very apt definition emphasizing that conflict is about perception not necessarily real hard facts. It points to the emotional nature of conflict, by referring to a word like —care. It states that more than one party is involved and that there may be future component attached to it.

Flowing from above postulations, we can deduce that Conflict means to be in opposition to one another. It refers to disagreement between people or members of organizations. Such disagreement is inherent in relationships between all human beings. Larfela (1988) concurs with this view when he defines conflict as: "Part of the competition process that is basic to the survival and successful evolution of the species, homosapiens and to his search for new and better ways to cope with limited resources and stress from environmental change." According to this definition it is obvious that conflict always exists between people, groups of people, members of an organization and between organizations which are related in one way or another. Having established the above, we can further assert that there has been a transition in the way conflict has been viewed over time. Thakore (2013) identified the following views on conflict:

a. **Traditional School View of Conflict:** This school views conflicts as bad for communities because it is disruptive, unnatural and represents a form of deviant behaviour which, should be controlled and changed if the communal objectives are to be achieved. To the traditional school, conflict situations can have tragic consequences for some people and adverse effect on communities. General view was that conflict indicates a malfunction within a group and must be avoided. This view proposed that very little value ever stemmed from conflict Robbins (2005) called this the traditional view.

b. **The Inter actionist school view of Conflict:** Townsend (1985) sees conflict as a sign of a communal existence. A good manager according to him, does not try to eliminate conflict, he tries to keep it from wasting the energies of his people... if you are the leader and your people fight you openly when they think you are wrong, that's healthy. If your people fight each other openly in your presence for what they believed in - that's healthy. But keep all the conflict eyeball to eyeball. Robins (1998) believes that conflict is a positive force and necessary for a united existence of the people in communities. This approach encourages a minimum level of conflict within the group in order to encourage self-criticism, change and innovation and to help prevent apathy or too great a tolerance for harmony and the status quo. Conflict is an inevitable feature of communal life and should be judged by its own performance.

c. **Integrationist school view of Conflict:** This is the most recent perspective and explicitly argues that some conflict should not only be seen as good or bad but rather that some conflict is absolutely necessary for a group to perform effectively.

However, Abiodun (2014) is of the view that the easiest way to understand the term "conflict" is to divide theories of conflict into functional, situational and interactive. The followers of the functional approach think that a conflict serves a social function and those who view a conflict as situational, suggest that conflict is an expression under certain situations. The third theory views conflict as interactive. Functionalists usually ask the questions: "Why is there conflict? What purpose does it serve?" while situationalists ask: "When do we have conflict? Under what circumstances does it occur?" Interactionalists are: "how is there conflict? What methods and mechanisms are used to express it?"

One of the representatives of the functionalist school was George Simmel, the German Sociologists. In 1955, he defined conflict as designed to resolve divergent dualisms; it is a way of achieving some kind of unity, even if it will be through the annihilation of one of the conflicting parties". According to Abiodun, conflict served as a social purpose and reconciliation came even with the total destruction of one party. Conflict socializes members into a group and reduces the tension between group members. Furthermore, Simmel determines three possible ways to end a conflict. Firstly, conflict may end with a victory of one party over another; secondly, the conflict can be resolved through compromise; and thirdly, through conciliation. However, not all conflicts may be ended as discussed. In 1967, Lewis Coser, gave the following definition of conflict: "The clash of values and interests,

the tension between what is and what some groups feel ought to be.” According to Coser (1967), conflict served the function of pushing society and was leading to new institutions, technology and economic systems. The most important contribution of Coser to conflict resolution was determination of the functional and dysfunctional roles of conflict.

A representative of the situationalist school, Bercovitch (1984), defines conflict as a situation which generates incommensurable goals or values among different parties. Folger (1993) defines conflict as “the interaction of interdependent people who perceive incompatible goals and interference from each other in achieving these goals”. This approach introduces two important concepts: Interdependence and perception. Interdependence is connected to such situations where one party’s future actions depend on another party’s actions. Another concept was mentioned by Tillett (1991). Cross, Names and Beck (1979) define conflict as differences between and among individuals. The differences are created by the conflict, for example, values, goals, motives, resources and ideas. Hocker and Wilmot (1985) define conflict as an expressed struggle between at least two interdependent parties who perceive incompatible goals, scarce rewards and interference from the other party in achieving their goals (Borisoff and Victor, 1998). Thomas (2005) defines conflict as a “disagreement in opinions between people or groups, due to differences in attitudes, beliefs, values or needs. In the business world, differences in such characteristics as work experience, personality, peer group, environment and situation, all lead to difference in personal attitudes, beliefs, values or needs”. From the above definitions, it is obvious that there is no just one practical definition of conflict. Each person has an individual way of thinking and behaves differently from others in similar situations. It can be concluded that conflict can affect everyone to varying extent (Leung, 2010).

Conflict as a Threat to Sustainable National Development

The existence of negative correlation between insecurity particularly violent conflict and economic development is not in doubt, what is not certain however is the extent to which insecurity affect development and the index or indices used in assessing development in general and economic development in particular. Irrespective of what measures are used in measuring economic development be it the traditional, economic development approach which focuses on national output; gross domestic product and per capita income, the social indicators approach which focuses on education (literacy and gross enrolment ratio), health (life Expectancy at Birth, Maternal Mortality ratio and Infant Mortality Ratio) and access to clean water and sanitation.

It could also be measured using composite index of development which includes: Physical Quality of Life Index (PQLI);

- i. Increase in life expectancy, fall in infant mortality rate and rise in basic literacy rate
- ii. Human Development Index (HDI) made up of social indicators such as life expectancy, adult literacy and years of schooling as well as GDP per capita i.e. longevity, educational attainment and decent standard of living,
- iii. Human Poverty Index (HPI) deprivation experience and inequality.
- iv. Regional Development Approach.

From the presentation so far, it is crystal clear that variant types of insecurity exist across different communities in different Geo-Political Zones. Despite variation in their forms and regions, the collective implications of insecurity as geographically presented has not only pose threats to National Economic Development in imaginary sense, but insecurity had reversed and made nonsense Economic Development of individuals, community and the National as a whole irrespective of which indices is adopted to measure National Economic Development.

It takes Traditional Approach which focused on improvement in material wellbeing of individuals and communities (Gross Domestic Products GDP and Gross Domestic Per Capita Income) the Social Indicator

Indices: Human Development Index (HDI), Physical Quality of Life Index (PQLI), Gender Development Index (GDI), Poverty Development Index (PDI) and Regional Development Index (RDI).

In essence, insecurity in Nigeria law lead to increase in the level of absolute poverty, threatened and destroyed Basic and Higher Education, disrupted Industrial Production, Agricultural Health Facilities and Widen Gender Disparity and Deprivation in distribution of Common Goods from the Common Humanity.

Phases and Pathways to Post Conflict Society

For development and sustainable development goals to be effective and successfully implemented a society that is just emerging and recovering from conflicts needs some semblance of peace security and stability before any serious stakeholder will deploy its resources both human and material. To achieve this objective such communities under conflict situation must pass through several phases to return to post conflict era these are

a. Recovery phase

This is a stage in the counter insurgency during which security and other counter insurgency actors and peace builders make a reasonable gain by recovering the communities and other areas hitherto lost to the insurgents

b. Stabilisation phase

During the stabilisation phases locals of the recovered community and people seeking refuge have gradually return and are facing difficulties in accessing social services and livelihood support as a result of collapse of socio – economic and political institutions . It is also characterised by shortage of source of livelihood as a result of ever increasing demand due to the increasing population. During this stabilisation periods, governments and other stakeholders such as development partner, UN specialised agencies and International Not for profit making organisation(INGOs) to move in and provide basically humanitarian and other live support services in line with their designate mandate.

c. Reconciliation and reintegration phase.

This the periods of healing conflicts wounds and forgives. It is periods during which peace building actors need to do serious fence mending and building social cohesion among conflicting parties. It is a periods during which community members displaced as a result of the conflicts, survivors of the conflicts traumatised need to be given proper trauma healing reintegrated and get accepted into the community.

d. Rehabilitation and reconstruction phase

Conflicts are mostly characterised by wanton destruction of properties and places of abode as well as functional socio- economic and political institutions partially or in some instances total and complete. This include but not limited to shelter, schools, security outfits, markets, hospitals and essential service. As normalcy return to communities ravaged by violent conflicts it is necessary that government at all level collaborate with development partners to reconstruct and in some cases rehabilitate those institutions and facilities in order to support community members afford at least a minimum descent lives. There are also people that have been affected directly by the violent conflicts which affect their, characters, psychological stability and physical wellbeing these people also need to be rehabilitated and reintegrated back into their communities.

e. Institution building and development sustainability phase

At this level of conflict recovery has been fully made people have been resettled and socio-political and economic activities fully pick up as normal business have return. It is therefore expected that the institutions weakened as a results of the violent conflict be strengthen win public confidence and support and be given capacity to function actively. At this juncture development partners, donors and non-governmental organisations but local and international are expected to withdraw and allow local institution and other community structures take over.

Strategies for Attaining Sustainable Development in Post Conflict Society

Achieving sustainable development in post-conflict societies is a complex and multifaceted process that requires a comprehensive and integrated approach. The following strategies are crucial for promoting long-term stability, peace, and sustainable development in these contexts (UNDP, 2018; OECD, 2018):

- i. **Good Governance and Rule of Law:** Establishing effective and accountable governance structures is essential for sustainable development. This includes strengthening institutions, promoting transparency, combating corruption, and ensuring the rule of law. Good governance enables equitable resource allocation, efficient service delivery, and the protection of human rights, which are crucial for sustainable development.
- ii. **Peacebuilding and Conflict Resolution:** Building sustainable peace is a fundamental prerequisite for development in post-conflict societies. This involves engaging in inclusive and participatory peace processes, promoting dialogue and reconciliation, and addressing the root causes of the conflict. Peacebuilding efforts should focus on building trust, fostering social cohesion, and ensuring justice and accountability for past atrocities.
- iii. **Social Development and Humanitarian Assistance:** Investing in social development is critical for post-conflict societies to rebuild social fabric and address the needs of vulnerable populations. This includes providing access to education, healthcare, housing, and social protection programs. Humanitarian assistance should be integrated with development efforts to ensure the immediate needs of affected communities are met while also supporting long-term development goals.
- iv. **Economic Recovery and Reconstruction:** Economic revitalization is vital for postconflict societies to rebuild their economies and improve livelihoods. Strategies should focus on creating employment opportunities, promoting entrepreneurship, attracting investments, and diversifying the economy. Emphasis should be placed on inclusive economic growth that benefits all segments of society, including marginalized groups and conflict-affected populations.
- v. **Capacity Building and Institutional Strengthening:** Building the capacity of local institutions and communities is crucial for sustainable development. This involves providing training, technical assistance, and resources to enhance the skills and knowledge of individuals and institutions. Capacity building efforts should focus on promoting local ownership, empowering marginalized groups, and fostering participatory decision-making processes.
- vi. **Environmental Sustainability:** Promoting environmental sustainability is essential for long-term development in post-conflict societies. Strategies should focus on sustainable natural resource management, environmental conservation, and climate change adaptation. This includes promoting renewable energy, sustainable agriculture practices, and biodiversity conservation. Environmental sustainability contributes to resilience, reduces resource-based conflicts, and supports long-term development.
- vii. **Development of Post Conflict Development Master Plan for the Region:** developing a Master Plan for development of societies in the post-conflict phase is an indispensable and strategic phase of recovering from the conflict and a necessary step in analysing the physical, social and economic destructions of the conflict. The step would avail nations the opportunity to reconstruct, rehabilitate, resettle all communities affected by the conflict in a very scientific and logical manner. The master plan serves as a guide through which every action or action would be carried out in relation to post conflict recovery and sustainable development.

viii. **International Cooperation and Partnerships:** Collaboration between postconflict societies and the international community is essential for sustainable development. International cooperation can provide financial resources, technical expertise, and knowledge sharing. Partnerships with donor countries, multilateral organizations, civil society, and the private sector can support the implementation of development programs and ensure their sustainability.

Challenges to Post Conflict Sustainable Development in North-East Nigeria

Achieving sustainable development in a post conflicts societies required concerted coordinated efforts among all stakeholders. This makes achieving sustainable development a herculean task full of challenges. While post-conflict sustainable development is a crucial goal for North-East Nigeria, there are several challenges that can hinder progress and pose obstacles to achieving long-term stability and sustainable development. Some of the key challenges include:

i. **Limited Resources:** Most communities emerging from conflict in Nigeria face significant resource constraints, including limited financial resources, infrastructure, and human capital. Rebuilding economies and addressing the needs of conflictaffected populations require substantial investments, which may be difficult to mobilize in resource-constrained environments.

ii. **High Corrupt Practices:** The country's high level of corrupt practices that saw series of mismanagement of resources and diversion of public funds meant for development is a series impediment for sustainable development efforts as resources meant for societal progress are often channelled to private pockets at the detriment of the entire society.

iii. **Weak Institutions:** Post-conflict societies often have weak and fragile institutions, including governance structures, legal systems, and public administration. Weak institutions can hinder effective service delivery, undermine accountability, and impede progress towards sustainable development. Strengthening institutions and promoting good governance is crucial but can be a long and challenging process. iv. **High Poverty and Inequality:** Conflict exacerbates poverty and inequality, and post-conflict societies often face high levels of poverty and income disparities. Addressing poverty and inequality is essential for sustainable development, but it requires targeted policies and programs that promote inclusive growth and equitable distribution of resources.

v. **Poor Coordination among Development Actors:** Uncoordinated humanitarian and development response in a post-conflict society could lead to duplication of roles and waste of resources meant for sustainable development and recovery. The inability of government at all levels of government to coordinate their response in relation with those of private sector, civil society and international donor agencies or organisations will instead of contribute to progress limit the level and pace at which the attainment of sustainable development is made.

vi. **Social Cohesion and Reconciliation:** Rebuilding social cohesion and promoting reconciliation among different ethnic, religious, or political groups is a critical challenge in post-conflict societies. Deep-rooted divisions and grievances can impede trust-building and hinder efforts towards sustainable development. Promoting dialogue, truth and reconciliation processes, and inclusive decisionmaking can help address these challenges.

vii. **Security Risks and Fragility:** Post-conflict societies are often characterized by lingering security risks and fragility. The presence of armed groups, the proliferation of small arms and light weapons, and the potential for renewed violence can undermine development efforts. Ensuring security and stability is crucial for sustainable development, and efforts must be made to disarm and reintegrate former combatants and establish effective security institutions.

viii. **Environmental Degradation:** Conflict can lead to significant environmental degradation, including deforestation, pollution, and the destruction of ecosystems. Environmental challenges can have long-lasting impacts on sustainable development, affecting agriculture, water resources, and livelihoods. Addressing environmental degradation and promoting sustainable resource management is essential for long-term development.

ix. **Regional and Cross-border Dynamics:** The conflict in North-East Nigeria has regional dimensions, with spill-over effects and cross-border challenges. Poor regional cooperation and coordination will affect efforts towards addressing these challenges and promoting sustainable development. The movement of armed groups through the borders can complicate efforts towards sustainable development.

Addressing these challenges requires a comprehensive and integrated approach that combines political, social, economic, and environmental strategies. It involves building strong institutions, promoting inclusive governance, investing in human capital, addressing poverty and inequality, fostering social cohesion, ensuring security, and promoting sustainable resource management. International support and partnerships are also critical for overcoming these challenges and supporting post-conflict countries in their journey towards sustainable development (UN, 2015; UNDP, 2018; OECD, 2018).

CONCLUSION

The paper examines the attainment of sustainable development in a post conflict society with Nigeria as a unit of analysis. Consequently, upon the foregoing analysis, it is concluded that the 21st century has recorded sporadic rise in violent conflicts globally with the activities of deadly Boko Haram insurgency as the most daring conflict in Northeast Nigeria which affects its efforts towards sustainable development. However, the attainment of the sustainable development goals despite the lingering crises is still possible if the challenges can be addressed holistically by all actors in development business. Challenges as limited resources, corrupt practices, weak institutions, high poverty and inequality, poor regional coordination, and security risks and fragility must be addressed. For North-East Nigeria to attain sustainable development therefore, efforts must be made towards strategies as the enhancement of good governance and rule of law, facilitating effective peacebuilding and conflict resolution, promoting social development and humanitarian assistance, establishing economic recovery and reconstruction measures, funding capacity building and institutional strengthening, renewed international cooperation and partnerships, and development of post-conflict development master plan for the region, and

RECOMMENDATIONS

From the foregoing presentation and analysis, the following recommendation became eminent:

i. There is need for the federal and state government to expand and explore it search for source of funds to implement the SDGs in the post conflict society. This can be realised through entering consortium with many development partners, donor agencies and international financial institutions.

ii. There is need for synergy among key agencies of government responsible for the implementation of SDGs to partner with anti-corruption agencies to track, monitor and ensure judicious utilisation of funds earmarked for each project and programmes. This will go a long way in reducing wasteful bureaucracies and corruptions in the SDGs implementation process.

iii. There is need for aggressive advocacy especially among officials of the local government level to enable them actively participate in the implementation of the SDGs since it is local people that stand to benefits more in the SDGs.

iv. The federal government should set clear budgetary priority for the SDGs to avoid conflict of choice among several issue demanding for government attention in the post-conflict recovery periods,

REFERENCES

Abiodun, R (2014). Organizational conflicts: Causes, effects and remedies.

Applebaum, S; Abdallah, C; Shapiro, B. (1999), the self-directed team: a conflict resolution analysis. *Team Performance Management*, 5(2), 60-77.

Bohannan, P. (1967). Introduction: Law & warfare. In P. Bohannan, *Studies in the Anthropology of Conflict* (xv-xiv). University of Texas Press.

Colser, A. (1964). Conflict. In *Dictionary of the Social Sciences* (123-124). The Free Press. Coser, L.A. (1967). *The Functions of Conflict*. Routledge.

Froyd, J. (2019). *Understanding conflict management*.

Hocker, J. I. & Wilmot, W. (1985). *Interpersonal Conflict Dubuque*, IOWA: Wmc. Brown Publisher.

Larfela, R.A. (1988). Interdepartmental Conflict.

Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development [OECD] (2018). Promoting sustainable development in fragile and conflict-affected situations.

Osipova, E. (1989). Emile Durkhiem's sociology. In I. S. Kon (ed.) *A History of Classical Sociology* (206-254). Progress Publishers.

Robbin,S & Seema, S. (2006). *Conflict and negotiation from organizational behaviour*. Pearson Education.

Schellenberg, A. (1996). *Conflict resolution: Theory, research and practice*. State University of New York Press.

Schermerhorn, J. Hunt, G. & Osborn, R. (1997). *Conflict and negotiation from organizational behaviour*. John Wiley and Sons Ltd.

Seymour, S. (1986). *Macmillan dictionary of anthropology*. Macmillan Press Ltd.

Taddesse B. (1988). *Traditional warfare among the Guji of Southern Ethiopia*. [Master Thesis, Michigan State University].

Thakore, D. (2013) Conflict and conflict management.

United Nations Development Programme [UNDP] (2018). *Africa human development report 2016: Accelerating gender equality and women's empowerment in Africa*.

United Nations. (2017). *Resolution adopted by the general Assembly: Works of the statistical commission pertaining to the 2030 Agenda for sustainable development archived 1st August 2021*. United Nations.